

COMPRESSION MOLDING OF GLASS FIBER-REINFORCED POLYPROPYLENE: ANISOTROPIC FLOW KINEMATICS

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ABSTRACT

The interaction between flow and fiber orientation during processing has a large influence on the final properties of a discontinuous fiber composite. A squeeze flow rheometer is used to investigate the effect of an initial fiber orientation distribution (FOD) upon the flow kinematics of discontinuous glass fiber-reinforced polypropylene during compression molding. The observed flow is highly anisotropic, being almost one-dimensional with negligible flow along the direction of preferred fiber orientation. An analytical model based on dilute suspension theory that gives a good description of the flow behavior is proposed.

Keywords: Squeeze flow, anisotropy, fiber orientation, GMT.

1. INTRODUCTION

The rheology of discontinuous glass fiber-reinforced polymers in compression molding has received increasing interest during the last decade; this is true for both thermosetting and the more recent thermoplastic materials. A compression-molded fiber-filled thermoplastic can be regarded as a planar fiber suspension and its rheological behavior depends on factors such as matrix properties, fiber orientation distribution (FOD), fiber length distribution, and fiber content.

Most modeling efforts have focused on thermosetting systems such as sheet molding compound (SMC). Current models are based on either of two entirely different kinematic assumptions. Early models [1,2] were derived from isothermal lubrication theory, where the flow is described by a generalized Hele-Shaw model with a no-slip condition at the mold surfaces. These give a good description of the flow front progression for thin parts, but poor results for thicker parts. Later, Barone and Caulk [3] modeled SMC as a two-dimensional sheet that undergoes a uniform extension, and slips relative to the mold surface. Their model has been experimentally verified for SMC for both thin and thick parts [4].

The same models have also been used for glass mat-reinforced thermoplastics (GMT), both directly and with modifications to include different transverse and in-plane viscosities, power

Figure 1: Layer structure.

law behavior, and fiber orientation [5,6,7]. Investigations involving fiber orientation are limited to effects of flow upon fiber orientation and disregard the effect of fiber orientation upon the flow behavior. However, it has been observed that some commercial materials have an inherent preferred orientation of the fibers as a result of a continuous manufacturing process. This can give rise to highly anisotropic flow kinematics of the material [8]. There is also a disagreement between the models and various experimental results, both regarding the through-the-thickness velocity distribution and the boundary conditions (slip or no-slip) [6,9]. This paper presents the results of an investigation of the in-plane and through-the-thickness flow kinematics of a commercial discontinuous glass fiber-reinforced polypropylene sheet in compression molding with special emphasis on the effect of an initial, anisotropic in-plane FOD.

2. MATERIAL CHARACTERIZATION

Experiments were performed using a commercial thermoplastic composite from AZDEL, Inc., with discontinuous glass fibers and polypropylene matrix. The fiber length and diameter are approximately 12 mm and 12 μm , respectively, and the original specimen thickness was between 3.3 mm and 3.7 mm. The fiber content by weight was measured by ashing several specimens and taking an average of the values obtained, and the volumetric concentration was calculated using $\rho_{\text{glass}} = 2.60 \text{ g/cm}^3$ and $\rho_{\text{pp}} = 0.905 \text{ g/cm}^3$. The content by weight was found to be 19.6% and the content by volume 7.8%. The fiber orientation distributions were measured by image analysis of polished sections parallel to the x,y-plane. This technique has been described elsewhere [10].

The AZDEL process resembles a continuous paper-making process, and as such it imparts a preferred fiber orientation to the material. The macroscopic structure and homogeneity of the fiber reinforcement could be examined by burning the matrix off several specimens. The material displays a clear layered structure, with variations in both the in-plane FOD and in the out-of-plane FOD. It was observed that the material has a preferred orientation in the machine direction except for a thin, 0.5–0.8 mm, bottom layer with perpendicular orientation and some out-of-plane orientation, see schematic in *Figure 1*. The coordinate system for the analysis is chosen with the 1-direction corresponding to the machine direction. In *Table 1* the angle of preferred in-plane orientation is given, in degrees, for the main and the bottom layer together with values for some of the components of the orientation tensor (see, e.g. [11]) with respect to its principal axes. The definition of the orientation angles is shown in *Figure 2*. In the following, the discussion refers to the main layer unless stated otherwise.

3. SQUEEZE FLOW EXPERIMENTS

An Interlaken model 3310 servo-hydraulic load frame with a 2.2 kN or a 10 kN load cell was used as a squeeze flow rheometer with the test set-up schematically shown in *Figure 3*. Each specimen was placed between the preheated parallel plates for 10 minutes to achieve isothermal test conditions at 200°C. It was thereafter compressed to a given degree of its initial thickness, and then cooled down to 125°C. The displacement rate was kept constant at 0.6 mm/min for all tests, and the specimen boundary was always kept within the boundaries of

Figure 2: Definition of orientation angles.

Table 1: Fiber orientation

Plane	φ	a_{1111}	a_{2222}	a_{1122}
Main layer	0	0.7453	0.0950	0.0799
Bottom layer	90	0.6347	0.1505	0.1034

the 110 mm diameter plates. The platen surfaces were cleaned after every test and a thin layer of mold release agent was added to ensure constant surface conditions. The various degrees of compression, together with the specimen diameters can be seen in *Table 2*.

The preferred orientation direction was marked on all specimens so that it was always distinguishable before and after a test. The initial boundary geometry of some specimens was marked, and in certain experiments, colored inserts of neat polypropylene, 1.5 mm in diameter, were used in order to study the through-the-thickness deformation profile. The inserts were placed at equal intervals in a symmetric arrangement along the 1- and 2-axes. The boundary geometry of the compressed samples was measured after completion of the test. Sections were made through the specimens with the inserts in order to study the deformation profile under an optical microscope. The other specimens were ashed for one hour at 600°C to study the deformed configuration of the fiber bed.

4. OBSERVED FLOW KINEMATICS

A typical boundary geometry evolution is shown in *Figure 4*. The principal in-plane flow pattern was strongly anisotropic with practically all the flow in the 2-direction, perpendicular to the direction of preferred fiber orientation. The through-the-thickness deformation profile was roughly parabolic, with little or no wall slip.

The picture is complicated by the presence of the bottom layer, which, due to its different orientation, flows mainly in the 1-direction. This layer also flowed much less than the main layer. This is probably due to a higher shear viscosity deriving from its higher degree of

Figure 3: Test set-up.

Table 2: Test configurations

Reduction of initial thickness in %	25mm	35mm	50mm	75mm
20	x	x	x	x
30	x	x	x	x
40	x	x	x	x
50	x	x	x	-
60	x	x	x	-

out-of-plane orientation. An attempt was made to remove the bottom layer by machining in order to study the flow of the main layer by itself. But this created a new problem: Flow mainly occurred at the machined surface, most likely due to a reduction of the fiber length, and thereby of the viscosity. The results reported in the following thus refer to the behavior of the main layer even though the bottom layer was preserved.

The schematics of the deformed cross section along the 1- and 2-directions shown in *Figures 5* and *6* are based on observations from ashed samples as well as from samples with inserts. The profiles suggest that the bottom layer flows only in the 1-direction and the main layer only in the 2-direction. That is, each layer flows transversely to its direction of preferred orientation, the longitudinal flow being negligible. Note that the deformation of the main layer in the 1-direction is a pure translation, if somewhat arbitrary.

The 35 mm, 50 mm, and 75 mm specimens all follow the same trend for the flow development. It could be seen from observations made during the compression, after the compression, and of the deformation of the inserts, that the flow starts in the 1-direction, close to the mid-plane of the main layer. The specimens compressed 20% show very little deformation, which can be attributed to the expelling of air from the specimen, while the specimens compressed 60% display a large interaction between the main and the bottom layers making it impossible to clearly distinguish between the two. The results from these two degrees of compression have therefore been excluded from the analysis below.

Except for the smallest samples ($\varnothing 25$ mm), the sample size did not seem to affect the

Figure 4: Boundary profile evolution.

Figure 5: Deformation profile in the 1-direction.

Figure 6: Deformation profile in the 2-direction.

observed flow kinematics. In the 25 mm sample the fiber bed remained almost completely immobile and the resin alone percolated out as the sample was compressed. This is interpreted as a sample size effect: If the sample size is too close to the fiber length, cutting the sample destroys the homogeneity of the structure; a major portion of the fibers will have their centers located close to the center of the specimen and will remain approximately stationary. This initiates fiber/matrix segregation, and as the fiber volume fraction in the center increases, the segregation is further enhanced by mechanical interlocking of the fiber network.

5. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

For a non-aligned, dilute fiber suspension the constitutive equation given by Hinch and Leal [12] reduces to

$$\sigma_{ij} = -P\delta_{ij} + 2\eta d_{ij}(1 + 2\Phi) + \frac{(l/d)^2}{2\ln(2l/d) - 3}\Phi\eta a_{ijkl}d_{kl}, \quad (1)$$

where P is the hydrostatic pressure, δ_{ij} is the unit tensor, η is the solvent viscosity, d_{ij} is the rate-of-deformation tensor, l is the fiber length, d is the fiber diameter, Φ is the volumetric concentration of fibers, and a_{ijkl} is the fourth-order orientation tensor. Arguing that the anisotropic in-plane deformation is governed by the in-plane extensional viscosities, we consider the case of pure extension; this is the case obtained in the limit of large sample thickness.

Thus we make the kinematic assumptions that all shear rates vanish ($d_{ij} = 0$, $i, j \neq 0$) and that the material is incompressible ($d_{ii} = 0$). We can now describe the in-plane deformations by the stretch ratio in the 1 and 2 directions

$$R_{12} = \frac{r_1 - r_0}{r_2 - r_0}, \quad (2)$$

where r_1 and r_2 are the radii after deformation along the x_1 and x_2 axes, respectively, and r_0 is the initial radius of the sample. For this flow, the stretch ratio can be derived from Eq. 1 as

$$R_{12} = \frac{a_{1122} - a_{1111}}{a_{1122} - a_{2222}}, \quad (3)$$

if

$$\frac{(l/d)^2}{2\ln(2l/d) - 3}\Phi \gg 1, \quad (4)$$

which condition is fulfilled by our suspension.

The main layer comprises, as discussed above, very thin layers having slightly different FODs. The deformation of some of these layers was measured on ashed samples and the stretch ratio was calculated and compared with the analytical model. This comparison is shown in *Figure 7* for the samples tested. As shown the rather simple model predicts fairly well the actual deformation for the main layer. The experimental data suggest that the flow becomes more isotropic toward larger deformations; this is expected, since the flow should tend to randomize the FOD. The measurements have a relative error of around 10% due to difficulties in measuring the very small deformations in the 1-direction.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The GMT material studied contained layers of different preferred fiber orientations. The initial flow in each layer was practically one-dimensional: The flow rate in the direction of preferred

Figure 7: Comparison between analytical and experimental results.

fiber orientation was negligible compared to that in the transverse direction. This shows that the extensional viscosities strongly control the flow kinematics.

Little or no wall slip was observed, and no plug flow was exhibited by the treated material; the velocity profile is nearly parabolic, the observed fluctuations being due to the material inhomogeneity.

An analytical expression based on classical dilute suspension theory successfully describes the anisotropic deformation of each layer.

A sample size effect was observed: The 25mm samples exhibited strong fiber-matrix separation, with the fiber bed almost completely immobile and the matrix percolating out of it. This behavior was not observed in larger samples ($\geq 35\text{mm}$). We conclude that this is a boundary effect which occurs as the sample size approaches the fiber length.

We finally conclude, based on the results of these isothermal tests, that the initial fiber orientation does play an important role in the mold-filling stage of compression molding. Our understanding of the interaction between flow and orientation is still incomplete, and further investigations with larger specimens, higher deformation rates, and nonisothermal conditions are necessary.

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